

2D Green's functions for an elastic layer on a rigid support loaded by an internal point force

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Abstract

The problem of a homogeneous isotropic elastic layer resting on a rigid base and loaded by an internal point force is analytically investigated under plane strain conditions. The displacement field is searched as the superposition of a particular solution (doublet state) and a homogeneous solution which allows satisfying the boundary conditions at the upper and lower boundaries of the layer. The displacement field is represented through convergent Fourier integral transforms. A closed form solution in the transformed domain is found. Then, the displacement and stress fields are assessed by numerical inversion of transforms. Results concerning both the displacements and stresses for different positions of the load application point are reported and compared to FEM solution, finding very good agreement. The solutions obtained for horizontal and vertical point forces define the Green's functions for the layer, which can be used to describe the mechanical interaction between the layer and an embedded inclusion. As a striking application, the interaction between the elastic layer and an embedded laterally loaded pile has been finally addressed, finding the contact pressure and, in turn, the internal forces in the pile.

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1. Introduction

The contact problem between an elastic layer and an embedded (elastic or rigid) body has been widely investigated under plane strain conditions owing to its noteworthy practical relevance to handle a variety of engineering matters. In particular, in the framework of civil engineering, the bearing capacity of floating foundations of buildings (e.g. beam-like foundations, footings, mat foundations) is often performed by considering the mechanical interaction between a stiff structure in (unilateral or bilateral) contact with an elastic layer of finite height within a two-dimensional framework. Although the behavior of a finite layer differs from that of an elastic half-plane, in some circumstances a preliminary solution can be obtained based on the 2D Boussinesq solution, owing to the local character of the problem. For instance, the stress analysis and the buckling problem of a Timoshenko beam in contact with an elastic support have been recently performed based on the Green function for an elastic half-plane [? ?]. However, proper adjustments to extend the 2D Boussinesq solution to layers of finite height can be handled based, for example, on strain energy equivalence arguments [?]. However, when accurate results are required, or when the size of the loaded region is comparable with the height of the hosting layer, the Boussinesq solution can lead to rough predictions, especially for what concerns the displacement field, and accounting for the actual height of the bearing layer becomes mandatory [?].

A variety of studies concerning an elastic layer of finite height coated by stiffeners or indented at its surfaces can be found in Literature [? ? ? ? ? ? ? ? ? ? ? ?], with direct applications in the framework of biomechanics, mechanical behavior of MEMS and NEMS, structural mechanics, geomechanics, etc. A comprehensive study about contact problems involving also elastic layers of finite thickness can be found in the textbook by [?]. In some cases, solutions

for the elastic layer may be useful for validating solutions obtained in the form of Fourier series for elastic (isotropic or anisotropic) plates under similar loading (e.g. [?]). The solutions of the problem of an elastic layer supported by a rigid base under various loading conditions applied at its surface are reported in the textbook [?]. In that reference, the effects of rough and smooth rigid bases at the bottom of the layer, together with a finite lateral extent of the layer, can be found also.

In all the aforementioned studies, the layer is loaded at its free surface(s). However, in many noteworthy applications the elastic layer interacts with an embedded body. In this case, the layer is subject to internal loading transmitted by the body along its contour. Although the analytical solution for a half plane and a half space loaded by an interior point load was provided by Melan (1932) and Mindlin (1953), respectively [? ?], no closed form solution of the problem of an elastic layer of finite height loaded by an internal point force can be found in Literature. The latter problem is partially addressed in [?] by representing the displacement field through the Marguerre solution. In that reference, the solution is sought as a sum of a particular solution, connected to the point load acting inside the layer, and a homogeneous solution, which allows satisfying the boundary conditions (BCs) at the boundaries. However, no results have been reported in that reference, and the accuracy of the obtained numerical solution has not been discussed at all.

In the present work, the analytical study of an infinite elastic layer supported by a rigid base and loaded by an arbitrary internal point load has been performed. The two loading cases of horizontal and vertical point loads have been considered separately. For each case, a double force system with equal and opposite forces in an infinite two-dimensional elastic solid under plane strain condition has been assumed as the particular solution. The corresponding displacement field displays logarithmic singularity at the load application point and it is regular at infinity. Then, an auxiliary solution satisfying the homogeneous equations of motion has been added to the fundamental one to match the BCs at the free surface and at the fixed bottom as well. Owing to the geometric

layout, sine and cosine Fourier transforms representation has been adopted for
60 the unknown displacement field. Due to the singular nature of the problem, the
integral transforms of the particular solution are divergent at the load appli-
cation point. Therefore, a special attention is paid on properly calculating the
inverse Fourier transforms, by grouping together the most singular terms and
calculating them analytically. Then, the remaining convergent integrals have
65 been assessed accurately through the Gauss-Laguerre quadrature rule. Main
results in terms of displacements and stresses inside the layer varying the load
application point have been reported and discussed. Moreover, the analytical
predictions are validated against Finite Element Method (FEM) simulations
and a good agreement is found between analytic and numerical predictions.
70 Finally, the relevant application of a laterally loaded pile embedded within the
elastic layer has been considered too, providing the contact pressure distribution
at the interface and, in turn, those of the shearing force and bending moment
along the pile. The analytical approach developed here is thus more rigorous
and realistic than those based on the Winkler's hypothesis, where the pile is re-
75 garded as a beam resting on elastic supports, and the soil reaction is assumed to
be proportional to deflection occurring at the same point. Using [?] formulae
to determine soil displacements and the integral equation method of analysis, [?]
] provided a general solution to the problem of a laterally loaded pile embedded
in a homogeneous linear and isotropic elastic half-space. The present results
80 thus extend the work of Poulos (1971) to the case of a pile embedded in an
elastic layer supported by a rigid foundation. The newly established solution
offers satisfactory predictions in comparison with numerical approaches. More-
over, the current solutions are applicable to various boundary conditions, and
any pile-soil relative stiffness.

85 **2. Problem formulation**

Let us consider a homogeneous and isotropic elastic layer of height h , per-
fectly bounded to an underlying rigid support and a Cartesian reference system

Oxy whose origin is placed at the bottom of the layer, Figure 1. The elastic layer

Figure 1: Elastic layer of finite height and infinitely extended subjected to an internal point force.

is considered infinitely extended along the x -direction and it is characterized by
 90 the shear modulus μ and Poisson's ratio ν .

The problem here addressed consists in the determination of the displacement field in the elastic layer induced by the application of a point force \mathbf{F} acting at the internal point $(0, c)$ of the layer. The components of the point force \mathbf{F} are denoted with F_x and F_y and act along the x and y directions, respectively.
 95 The effect of each load component will be investigated in the following sections separately.

The analysis will be carried out in the quasi-static regime neglecting the inertial terms. Because of the context of linear elasticity, the solutions of these two loading cases can be superposed and combined for investigating more complex loading conditions. The problem is approached in terms of displacements
 100 method starting from the Navier equations in the xy -plane [?], namely

$$\begin{aligned} (1 - 2\nu) \frac{\partial^2 u(x, y)}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2 v(x, y)}{\partial x \partial y} + 2(1 - \nu) \frac{\partial^2 u(x, y)}{\partial x^2} + (1 - 2\nu) \frac{F_x}{\mu} \delta(x) \delta(y - c) &= 0, \\ (1 - 2\nu) \frac{\partial^2 v(x, y)}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 u(x, y)}{\partial x \partial y} + 2(1 - \nu) \frac{\partial^2 v(x, y)}{\partial y^2} + (1 - 2\nu) \frac{F_y}{\mu} \delta(x) \delta(y - c) &= 0, \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

for $x \in \mathbb{R}$ and $y \in [0, h]$, where functions $u(x, y)$ and $v(x, y)$ are the unknown displacement components along the x and y axes, respectively, and $\delta(x)$ denotes the Dirac delta function.

105 The formulation of the boundary value problem requires the imposition of the kinematic boundary conditions at the interface with the rigid support

$$u(x, 0) = v(x, 0) = 0, \quad \forall x \in \mathbb{R}, \quad (2)$$

together with the vanishing of the normal and shear stress components at the free surface of the layer, namely

$$\sigma_{yy}(x, h) = \sigma_{xy}(x, h) = 0, \quad \forall x \in \mathbb{R}, \quad (3)$$

where stress components in the layer under plane strain conditions read

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{xx}(x, y) &= \frac{2\mu}{1-2\nu} \left[(1-\nu) \frac{\partial u(x, y)}{\partial x} + \nu \frac{\partial v(x, y)}{\partial y} \right], \\ \sigma_{yy}(x, y) &= \frac{2\mu}{1-2\nu} \left[(1-\nu) \frac{\partial v(x, y)}{\partial y} + \nu \frac{\partial u(x, y)}{\partial x} \right], \\ \sigma_{xy}(x, y) &= \mu \left[\frac{\partial u(x, y)}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v(x, y)}{\partial x} \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

110 The solution of the PDEs system (1) will be looked for by introducing the Fourier transforms of the displacement components. As mentioned above, the two loading cases along the x and y axes will be separately investigated, and in each case the solution of the PDEs system (1) will be split into the homogeneous and particular solutions. In both loading cases, the Kelvin solution for a point
115 load acting in an infinite elastic plane [?] will be taken as particular solution. Therefore the homogeneous solution of the PDEs system (1) will be superposed to the particular solution in order to fulfill the BCs (2) and (3).

2.1. Point load acting in the x -axis direction

The problem of a point load F_x acting at the point $(0, c)$ in the elastic
120 layer is considered, see Figure 1. To this aim, let us introduce the following dimensionless quantities

$$\begin{aligned} [\xi, \eta, \tau] &= [x, y, c]/h, & [U, V] &= [u, v] 8\pi\mu(1-\nu)/F_x, \\ [\Sigma_{xx}, \Sigma_{yy}, \Sigma_{xy}] &= [\sigma_{xx}, \sigma_{yy}, \sigma_{xy}] 8\pi(1-\nu)h/F_x. \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

Correspondingly, the governing equilibrium eqns (1) assume the following dimensionless form:

$$\begin{aligned} (1-2\nu)\frac{\partial^2 U(\xi, \eta)}{\partial \eta^2} + \frac{\partial V(\xi, \eta)}{\partial \xi \partial \eta} + 2(1-\nu)\frac{\partial^2 U(\xi, \eta)}{\partial \xi^2} + 8\pi(1-\nu)(1-2\nu)\delta(\xi)\delta(\eta-\tau) &= 0, \\ (1-2\nu)\frac{\partial^2 V(\xi, \eta)}{\partial \xi^2} + \frac{\partial U(\xi, \eta)}{\partial \xi \partial \eta} + 2(1-\nu)\frac{\partial^2 V(\xi, \eta)}{\partial \eta^2} &= 0, \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

for $\xi \in \mathbb{R}$ and $\eta \in [0, 1]$. Let us assume as particular solution the double force system formed by two equal and opposite forces acting along different lines of action. This doublet state can be obtained from the superposition of two Kelvin states corresponding to the load component F_x applied at the point $(0, c)$ and the load component $-F_x$ applied at the point $(0, -c)$, namely[?]

$$\begin{aligned} U_p(\xi, \eta) &= -\frac{(\eta-\tau)^2}{\xi^2 + (\eta-\tau)^2} + \frac{(\eta+\tau)^2}{\xi^2 + (\eta+\tau)^2} - \frac{3-4\nu}{2} \ln \frac{\xi^2 + (\eta-\tau)^2}{\xi^2 + (\eta+\tau)^2}, \\ V_p(\xi, \eta) &= \frac{\xi(\eta-\tau)}{\xi^2 + (\eta-\tau)^2} - \frac{\xi(\eta+\tau)}{\xi^2 + (\eta+\tau)^2}. \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

For this situation, the two forces produce a moment about the z -axis, which is perpendicular to the plane of the forces. For this particular choice, the logarithmic singularity of the displacement field at infinity, which is typical of the Kelvin solution for a single point force, disappears and thus the inverse Fourier transforms of the displacements (7) and (8) can be calculated easily. According to the loading symmetry, the use of the cosine and sine Fourier transforms is made for the horizontal and vertical components of the displacement field, respectively. Let the cosine and sine Fourier transforms $\bar{U}_p(s, \eta)$ and $\bar{V}_p(s, \eta)$ of the displacement components (7) and (8) be defined as

$$\bar{U}_p(s, \eta) = \frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^\infty U_p(\xi, \eta) \cos s\xi d\xi, \quad \bar{V}_p(s, \eta) = \frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^\infty V_p(\xi, \eta) \sin s\xi d\xi, \quad (9)$$

where s is the transformed variable of ξ . Then, the corresponding inverse transforms are given by

$$U_p(\xi, \eta) = \int_0^\infty \bar{U}_p(s, \eta) \cos s\xi ds, \quad V_p(\xi, \eta) = \int_0^\infty \bar{V}_p(s, \eta) \sin s\xi ds. \quad (10)$$

140 The introduction of (7) and (8) in the integrals in (9) provides the following transforms of the particular solutions

$$\begin{aligned}\bar{U}_p(s, \eta) &= \frac{3-4\nu}{s} \left[e^{-|\eta-\tau|s} - e^{-(\eta+\tau)s} \right] + (\eta+\tau)e^{-(\eta+\tau)s} - |\eta-\tau|e^{-|\eta-\tau|s}, \\ \bar{V}_p(s, \eta) &= (\eta-\tau)e^{-|\eta-\tau|s} - (\eta+\tau)e^{-(\eta+\tau)s}.\end{aligned}\quad (11)$$

1

Let us denote with $U_h(\xi, \eta)$ and $V_h(\xi, \eta)$ the homogeneous solution of the PDEs system (6). Then, relations similar to (9) and (10) hold between the
145 functions $U_h(\xi, \eta)$ and $V_h(\xi, \eta)$ and their cosine and sine Fourier transforms $\bar{U}_h(s, \eta)$ and $\bar{V}_h(s, \eta)$. Thereby, the Fourier transforms of the homogeneous solution must satisfy the homogeneous form of the governing equilibrium eqns (6), namely

$$\begin{aligned}(1-2\nu)\bar{U}_h''(s, \eta) - 2(1-\nu)s^2\bar{U}_h(s, \eta) + s\bar{V}_h'(s, \eta) &= 0, \\ 2(1-\nu)\bar{V}_h''(s, \eta) - (1-2\nu)s^2\bar{V}_h(s, \eta) - s\bar{U}_h'(s, \eta) &= 0,\end{aligned}\quad (12)$$

for $s \geq 0$ and $\eta \in [0, 1]$, where prime denotes the derivative with respect to η .

150 It is easy to prove that solution of the linear and homogeneous ODEs system (12) admits the following representation

$$\begin{aligned}\bar{U}_h(s, \eta) &= [A_1(s) + \eta A_2(s)] \sinh \eta s + [A_3(s) + \eta A_4(s)] \cosh \eta s, \\ \bar{V}_h(s, \eta) &= \left[A_1(s) + \eta A_2(s) - \frac{3-4\nu}{s} A_4(s) \right] \cosh \eta s + \\ &\quad \left[A_3(s) + \eta A_4(s) - \frac{3-4\nu}{s} A_2(s) \right] \sinh \eta s,\end{aligned}\quad (13)$$

where the unknown functions $A_i(s)$, for $i = 1, 2, 3, 4$, must be determined by imposing the BCs (2) and (3). The substitution of relations (11) and (13) into the kinematic BCs (2) due to the rigid-support at the bottom of the layer then

¹In (11) we used the following results provided in [?] and their derivatives with respect to s

$$\int_0^\infty \frac{\cos s\xi}{\xi^2 + \beta^2} d\xi = \frac{\pi}{2\beta} e^{-\beta s}, \quad \int_0^\infty \log \frac{\xi^2 + \alpha^2}{\xi^2 + \beta^2} \cos s\xi d\xi = \frac{\pi}{s} [e^{-\beta s} - e^{-\alpha s}],$$

which hold for $\alpha \geq 0$ and $\beta \geq 0$.

155 provides the following two relations for the unknown functions

$$A_1(s) = \frac{3-4\nu}{s}A_4(s) + 2\tau e^{-\tau s}, \quad A_3(s) = 0. \quad (14)$$

Then, the introduction of relations (14) in eqns (13) provides

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{U}_h(s, \eta) &= \left[\frac{3-4\nu}{s}A_4(s) + 2\tau e^{-\tau s} \right] \sinh \eta s + \eta [A_2(s) \sinh \eta s + A_4(s) \cosh \eta s], \\ \bar{V}_h(s, \eta) &= -\frac{3-4\nu}{s}A_2(s) \sinh \eta s + 2\tau e^{-\tau s} \cosh \eta s + \\ &\quad \eta [A_2(s) \cosh \eta s + A_4(s) \sinh \eta s]. \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

The introduction of the transforms of displacement field into the boundary conditions (3) on the top of the layer, at $\eta = 1$, then requires

$$\begin{aligned} (1-\nu)\bar{V}'(s, 1) - \nu s\bar{U}(s, 1) &= 0, \\ \bar{U}'(s, 1) + s\bar{V}(s, 1) &= 0, \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

for $s \geq 0$. By using relations (11) and (15), the boundary conditions (16) at the
160 free surface of the layer provides the following linear system of equations for the unknown functions $A_2(s)$ and $A_4(s)$

$$\begin{aligned} \begin{bmatrix} s \cosh s - (1-2\nu) \sinh s & s \sinh s + 2(1-\nu) \cosh s \\ s \sinh s - 2(1-\nu) \cosh s & s \cosh s + (1-2\nu) \sinh s \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} A_2(s) \\ A_4(s) \end{bmatrix} &= \\ \begin{bmatrix} -(2-2\nu-s)e^{-(1+\tau)s} + [2-2\nu-(1-\tau)s]e^{-(1-\tau)s} - \tau s e^{(1-\tau)s} \\ (1-2\nu-s)e^{-(1+\tau)s} - [1-2\nu-(1-\tau)s]e^{-(1-\tau)s} - \tau s e^{(1-\tau)s} \end{bmatrix}. \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

The system (17) can be solved for $A_2(s)$ and $A_4(s)$ as

$$\begin{aligned} A_2(s) &= \frac{1}{g(s)} \left\{ \tau s [(3-4\nu) \cosh \tau s + \cosh(2-\tau)s] + 2[2-6\nu+4\nu^2-s^2(1-\tau)] \sinh \tau s \right\}, \\ A_4(s) &= \frac{1}{g(s)} \left\{ \tau s [(3-4\nu) \sinh \tau s - \sinh(2-\tau)s] - 2s^2\tau \cosh \tau s - 2s(3-4\nu-s) \sinh \tau s \right. \\ &\quad \left. + 2e^{-s} [(1-2\nu)^2 \sinh s + 4(1-\nu)^2 \cosh s] \sinh \tau s \right\}, \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

being

$$g(s) = s^2 + (1-2\nu)^2 + (3-4\nu) \cosh^2 s. \quad (19)$$

From eqns (18) one has

$$A_2(s) = 2\tau s + o(s), \quad A_4(s) = 2\tau s + o(s), \quad (20)$$

165 as $s \rightarrow 0$. Therefore, from eqns (15) it follows that $\bar{U}_h(s, \eta)$ and $\bar{V}_h(s, \eta)$ are not singular as $s \rightarrow 0$ and thus they can be integrated to obtain the inverse Fourier cosine transform according to (10). Let us now investigate the asymptotic behavior of $\bar{U}_h(s, \eta)$ and $\bar{V}_h(s, \eta)$ as $s \rightarrow \infty$. From the results (18) one can observe that

$$\begin{aligned} A_2(s) &= \frac{2\tau s}{3-4\nu} e^{-s\tau} + 2 \left[-\frac{2(1-\tau)}{3-4\nu} s^2 + s\tau + 4 \frac{(1-\nu)(1-2\nu)}{3-4\nu} \right] e^{-s(2-\tau)} + O(s^3 e^{-s(2+\tau)}), \\ A_4(s) &= -\frac{2\tau s}{3-4\nu} e^{-\tau s} + 2 \left[\frac{2(1-\tau)}{3-4\nu} s^2 - s(2-\tau) + \frac{5-12\nu+8\nu^2}{3-4\nu} \right] e^{-s(2-\tau)} + O(s^3 e^{-s(2+\tau)}), \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

170 as $s \rightarrow \infty$. Therefore, the displacement transforms display regular behavior as $s \rightarrow 0$ as well as $s \rightarrow \infty$. Let us introduce the functions

$$\begin{aligned} a_2(s) &= A_2(s) - \frac{2\tau s}{3-4\nu} e^{-\tau s} - 2 \left[-\frac{2(1-\tau)}{3-4\nu} s^2 + s\tau + 4 \frac{(1-\nu)(1-2\nu)}{3-4\nu} \right] e^{-s(2-\tau)}, \\ a_4(s) &= A_4(s) + \frac{2\tau s}{3-4\nu} e^{-\tau s} - 2 \left[\frac{2(1-\tau)}{3-4\nu} s^2 - s(2-\tau) + \frac{5-12\nu+8\nu^2}{3-4\nu} \right] e^{-s(2-\tau)}, \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

which behave as $O(s^3 e^{-(2+\tau)s})$ as $s \rightarrow \infty$. Then, the Fourier transforms of the displacement fields become

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{U}(s, \eta) &= \frac{3-4\nu}{s} \left[e^{-s|\tau-\eta|} - e^{-s(\tau+\eta)} \right] - |\eta-\tau| e^{-s|\tau-\eta|} + \left(\tau + \eta - \frac{2\tau s \eta}{3-4\nu} \right) e^{-s(\tau+\eta)} + \\ &\quad - 2 \frac{5-12\nu+8\nu^2}{s} e^{-s(2-\tau)} \sinh \eta s - [(3-4\nu)(2-\eta-\tau) - 2s(1-\eta)(1-\tau)] e^{-s(2-\tau-\eta)} + \\ &\quad \left[(3-4\nu)(2-\tau) + \frac{\eta}{3-4\nu} - 2s(1+\eta-\tau) + \frac{4\eta s^2(1-\tau)}{3-4\nu} \right] e^{-s(2-\tau+\eta)} + \bar{U}^*(s, \eta), \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{V}(s, \eta) &= (\eta-\tau) e^{-s|\tau-\eta|} + \left(\tau - \eta + \frac{2s\tau\eta}{3-4\nu} \right) e^{-s(\tau+\eta)} - 8 \frac{1-3\nu+2\nu^2}{s} e^{-s(2-\tau)} \sinh \eta s + \\ &\quad [(3-4\nu)(\eta-\tau) + 2s(1-\eta)(1-\tau)] e^{-s(2-\tau-\eta)} - \\ &\quad \left[\frac{\eta}{3-4\nu} - (3-4\nu)\tau + 2s(1-\eta-\tau) + \frac{4\eta s^2(1-\tau)}{3-4\nu} \right] e^{-s(2-\tau+\eta)} + \bar{V}^*(s, \eta), \end{aligned}$$

where the functions

$$\bar{U}^*(s, \eta) = \frac{3-4\nu}{s} a_4(s) \sinh \eta s + \eta [a_2(s) \sinh \eta s + a_4(s) \cosh \eta s], \quad (24)$$

$$\bar{V}^*(s, \eta) = -\frac{3-4\nu}{s} a_2(s) \sinh \eta s + \eta [a_2(s) \cosh \eta s + a_4(s) \sinh \eta s], \quad (25)$$

175 can be integrated numerically. Indeed, according to the asymptotic behavior of $a_2(s)$ and $a_4(s)$ as $s \rightarrow \infty$, it is easy to prove that functions $\bar{U}^*(s, \eta)$ and $\bar{V}^*(s, \eta)$ are finite as $s \rightarrow 0$ and behave as $O(s^3 e^{-s(1+\tau-\eta)})$ as $s \rightarrow \infty$. The displacement field follows from the inverse cosine and sine Fourier transforms of (23) as

$$\begin{aligned} U(\xi, \eta) = & \frac{4\tau\eta\xi^2}{(\xi^2 + \eta^2 + \tau^2)^2 - 4\eta^2\tau^2} - \frac{2\tau\eta[(\tau + \eta)^2 - \xi^2]}{(3-4\nu)[\xi^2 + (\tau + \eta)^2]^2} + \\ & \frac{3-4\nu}{2} \ln \frac{\xi^2 + (\tau + \eta)^2}{\xi^2 + (\tau - \eta)^2} + \frac{5-12\nu+8\nu^2}{2} \ln \frac{\xi^2 + (2-\tau+\eta)^2}{\xi^2 + (2-\tau-\eta)^2} + U_R(\xi, \eta), \end{aligned} \quad (26)$$

$$\begin{aligned} V(\xi, \eta) = & \frac{4\tau\xi\eta(\eta - \tau)}{(\xi^2 + \eta^2 + \tau^2)^2 - 4\eta^2\tau^2} + \frac{4\tau\xi\eta(\tau + \eta)}{(3-4\nu)[\xi^2 + (\tau + \eta)^2]^2} \\ & - 4(1-2\nu)(1-\nu) \arctan \frac{2\eta\xi}{(2-\tau)^2 - \eta^2 + \xi^2} + V_R(\xi, \eta), \end{aligned}$$

180 where

$$\begin{aligned} U_R(\xi, \eta) = & -\frac{(3-4\nu)(2-\tau-\eta)^2}{(2-\tau-\eta)^2 + \xi^2} + \frac{(2-\tau+\eta)[\eta + (3-4\nu)^2(2-\tau)]}{(3-4\nu)[(2-\tau+\eta)^2 + \xi^2]} \\ & + \frac{2(1-\eta)(1-\tau)[(2-\tau-\eta)^2 - \xi^2]}{[(2-\tau-\eta)^2 + \xi^2]^2} - \frac{2(1-\tau+\eta)[(2-\tau+\eta)^2 - \xi^2]}{[(2-\tau+\eta)^2 + \xi^2]^2} \\ & + \frac{8\eta(1-\tau)(1-\tau+\eta)[(1-\tau+\eta)^2 - 3\xi^2]}{(3-4\nu)[(1-\tau+\eta)^2 + \xi^2]^3} + \int_0^\infty \bar{U}^*(s, \eta) \cos s\xi ds, \end{aligned} \quad (27)$$

$$\begin{aligned} V_R(\xi, \eta) = & \frac{\xi(3-4\nu)(\eta - \tau)}{(2-\eta-\tau)^2 + \xi^2} + \frac{\xi[(3-4\nu)^2\tau - \eta]}{(3-4\nu)[(2+\eta-\tau)^2 + \xi^2]} \\ & + \frac{4\xi(1-\eta)(1-\tau)(2-\eta-\tau)}{[(2-\eta-\tau)^2 + \xi^2]^2} - \frac{4\xi(1-\eta-\tau)(2+\eta-\tau)}{[(2+\eta-\tau)^2 + \xi^2]^2} \\ & - \frac{8\eta\xi(1-\tau)(3(2+\eta-\tau)^2 - \xi^2)}{(3-4\nu)[(2+\eta-\tau)^2 + \xi^2]^3} + \int_0^\infty \bar{V}^*(s, \eta) \sin s\xi ds, \end{aligned}$$

are regular functions of ξ, η and τ . Indeed, we extracted the regular part \bar{U}^* from the function \bar{U} , where \bar{U}^* is finite for $s = 0$ and behaves as $O(s^3 e^{-s(1+\tau)})$

as s tends to infinity. Therefore, the integral of the function \bar{U}^* for s ranging between 0 and infinity is also regular. In particular, the displacement along the
185 x direction at $\xi = 0$ is given by

$$U(0, \eta) = (3 - 4\nu) \ln \frac{\tau + \eta}{|\tau - \eta|} - \frac{2\tau\eta}{(3 - 4\nu)(\tau + \eta)^2} + (5 - 12\nu + 8\nu^2) \ln \frac{2 - \tau + \eta}{2 - \tau - \eta} + U_R(0, \eta), \quad (28)$$

where

$$U_R(0, \eta) = -3 + 4\nu + \frac{8\eta(1 - \tau)}{(3 - 4\nu)(1 - \tau + \eta)^3} + \frac{\eta + (3 - 4\nu)^2(2 - \tau)}{(3 - 4\nu)(2 - \tau + \eta)} + \frac{2(1 - \eta)(1 - \tau)}{(2 - \tau - \eta)^2} - \frac{2(1 - \tau + \eta)}{(2 - \tau + \eta)^2} + \int_0^\infty \bar{U}^*(s, \eta) ds, \quad (29)$$

is a regular function for $0 \leq \eta \leq 1$, being the function \bar{U}^* regular for $0 \leq \eta \leq 1$, as it follows from its definition (24).

2.2. Point load acting on the y -axis direction

190 The case of the load component F_y acting at the point $(0, c)$ in the elastic layer is investigated here, see Figure 1. As done in the previous section, we refer to the dimensionless quantities (5), where F_x is replaced by F_y .

In this case the equilibrium eqns (1) become

$$(1 - 2\nu) \frac{\partial^2 U(\xi, \eta)}{\partial \eta^2} + \frac{\partial V(\xi, \eta)}{\partial \xi \partial \eta} + 2(1 - \nu) \frac{\partial^2 U(\xi, \eta)}{\partial \xi^2} = 0, \quad (30)$$

$$(1 - 2\nu) \frac{\partial^2 V(\xi, \eta)}{\partial \xi^2} + \frac{\partial U(\xi, \eta)}{\partial \xi \partial \eta} + 2(1 - \nu) \frac{\partial^2 V(\xi, \eta)}{\partial \eta^2} + 8\pi(1 - \nu)(1 - 2\nu)\delta(\xi)\delta(\eta - \tau) = 0,$$

for $\xi \in \mathbb{R}$ and $\eta \in [0, 1]$. As a particular solution, we assume the double force
195 system formed by the load component F_y applied at the point $(0, c)$ and the load component $-F_y$ applied at the point $(0, -c)$, which admits the following displacement field [?]

$$U_p(\xi, \eta) = \frac{\xi(\eta - \tau)}{\xi^2 + (\eta - \tau)^2} - \frac{\xi(\eta + \tau)}{\xi^2 + (\eta + \tau)^2}, \quad (31)$$

$$V_p(\xi, \eta) = \frac{(\eta - \tau)^2}{\xi^2 + (\eta - \tau)^2} - \frac{(\eta + \tau)^2}{\xi^2 + (\eta + \tau)^2} - \frac{3 - 4\nu}{2} \ln \frac{\xi^2 + (\eta - \tau)^2}{\xi^2 + (\eta + \tau)^2}. \quad (32)$$

In this case the two forces are applied on the same line of action and thus they are self-balanced. As in the previous case, the displacement field is singular at

200 the point of application of the load and it is regular at infinity. According to the loading symmetry, the sine and cosine Fourier transforms $U_p(s, \eta)$ and $V_p(s, \eta)$ of the displacement field (31) and (32) are taken. They are defined as

$$\bar{U}_p(s, \eta) = \frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^\infty U_p(\xi, \eta) \sin s\xi d\xi, \quad \bar{V}_p(s, \eta) = \frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^\infty V_p(\xi, \eta) \cos s\xi d\xi, \quad (33)$$

respectively. The corresponding inverse transforms are given by

$$U_p(\xi, \eta) = \int_0^\infty \bar{U}_p(s, \eta) \sin s\xi ds, \quad V_p(\xi, \eta) = \int_0^\infty \bar{V}_p(s, \eta) \cos s\xi ds. \quad (34)$$

The introduction of (31) and (32) in the integrals in (33) then provides the
205 following transforms of the particular solution:

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{U}_p(s, \eta) &= e^{-|\eta-\tau|s}(\eta-\tau) - e^{-(\eta+\tau)s}(\eta+\tau), \\ \bar{V}_p(s, \eta) &= |\eta-\tau|e^{-|\eta-\tau|s} - (\eta+\tau)e^{-(\eta+\tau)s} + \frac{3-4\nu}{s} \left[e^{-|\eta-\tau|s} - e^{-(\eta+\tau)s} \right] \end{aligned} \quad (35)$$

Let us denote with $U_h(\xi, \eta)$ and $V_h(\xi, \eta)$ the general homogeneous solution of the PDEs system (30). Then, relations similar to those in (33) and (34) hold between the functions $U_h(\xi, \eta)$ and $V_h(\xi, \eta)$ and their sine and cosine Fourier transforms $\bar{U}_h(s, \eta)$ and $\bar{V}_h(s, \eta)$. It follows that the Fourier transforms of
210 the homogeneous solution must satisfy the homogeneous form of the governing equilibrium eqns (30), namely

$$\begin{aligned} (1-2\nu)\bar{U}_h''(s, \eta) - 2(1-\nu)s^2\bar{U}_h(s, \eta) - s\bar{V}_h'(s, \eta) &= 0, \\ 2(1-\nu)\bar{V}_h''(s, \eta) - (1-2\nu)s^2\bar{V}_h(s, \eta) + s\bar{U}_h'(s, \eta) &= 0, \end{aligned} \quad (37)$$

for $s \geq 0$ and $\eta \in [0, 1]$. The linear and homogeneous ODEs system (37) admits the following solution

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{U}_h(s, \eta) &= [C_1(s) + \eta C_2(s)] \cosh \eta s + [C_3(s) + \eta C_4(s)] \sinh \eta s, \\ \bar{V}_h(s, \eta) &= \left[\frac{3-4\nu}{s} C_2(s) - C_3(s) - \eta C_4(s) \right] \cosh \eta s + \\ &\quad \left[\frac{3-4\nu}{s} C_4(s) - C_1(s) - \eta C_2(s) \right] \sinh \eta s, \end{aligned} \quad (38)$$

where the unknown functions $C_i(s)$, for $i = 1, 2, 3, 4$, must be determined by
215 imposing the BCs (2) and (3). The introduction of relations (36) and (38) into

the kinematic BCs (2) then provides the following two relations for the unknown functions

$$C_1(s) = 2\tau e^{-\tau s}, \quad C_3(s) = \frac{3-4\nu}{s}C_2(s). \quad (39)$$

The introduction of the transforms of displacement field into the boundary conditions (3) on the top of the layer, at $\eta = 1$, yields

$$\begin{aligned} (1-\nu)\bar{V}'(s,1) + \nu s\bar{U}(s,1) &= 0, \\ \bar{U}'(s,1) - s\bar{V}(s,1) &= 0, \end{aligned} \quad (40)$$

220 for $s \geq 0$. Then, by using relations (39), the boundary conditions at the free surface of the layer (40) provide the following linear system of equations for the unknown functions $C_2(s)$ and $C_4(s)$:

$$\begin{aligned} &\begin{bmatrix} s \sinh s + 2(1-\nu) \cosh s & s \cosh s - (1-2\nu) \sinh s \\ s \cosh s + (1-2\nu) \sinh s & s \sinh s - 2(1-\nu) \cosh s \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} C_2(s) \\ C_4(s) \end{bmatrix} = \\ &\begin{bmatrix} -(1-2\nu+s)e^{-(1+\tau)s} + [1-2\nu+(1-\tau)s]e^{-(1-\tau)s} - \tau s e^{(1-\tau)s} \\ (2-2\nu+s)e^{-(1+\tau)s} - [2-2\nu+(1-\tau)s]e^{-(1-\tau)s} - \tau s e^{(1-\tau)s} \end{bmatrix}. \end{aligned} \quad (41)$$

The system (41) can be solved for $C_2(s)$ and $C_4(s)$ as

$$\begin{aligned} C_2(s) &= \frac{1}{g(s)} \left\{ -\tau s [\cosh(2-\tau)s + (3-4\nu) \cosh \tau s] + 2[2-6\nu+4\nu^2-s^2(1-\tau)] \sinh \tau s \right\}, \\ C_4(s) &= \frac{1}{g(s)} \left\{ \tau s [\sinh(2-\tau)s - (3-4\nu) \sinh \tau s] - 2s^2\tau \cosh \tau s + 2s(3-4\nu+s) \sinh \tau s \right. \\ &\quad \left. + 2e^{-s} [(1-2\nu)^2 \sinh s + 4(1-\nu)^2 \cosh s] \sinh \tau s \right\}, \end{aligned} \quad (42)$$

where function $g(s)$ has been defined in (19). From eqns (42) one has

$$C_2(s) = -\frac{2\nu\tau s}{1-\nu} + o(s), \quad C_4(s) = 2\tau s + o(s), \quad (43)$$

225 as $s \rightarrow 0$, and

$$\begin{aligned} C_2(s) &= -\frac{2\tau s}{3-4\nu} e^{-s\tau} - 2 \left[\frac{2(1-\tau)}{3-4\nu} s^2 + s\tau - 4 \frac{(1-\nu)(1-2\nu)}{3-4\nu} \right] e^{-s(2-\tau)} + O(s^3 e^{-s(2+\tau)}), \\ C_4(s) &= \frac{2\tau s}{3-4\nu} e^{-\tau s} + 2 \left[\frac{2(1-\tau)}{3-4\nu} s^2 + s(2-\tau) + \frac{5-12\nu+8\nu^2}{3-4\nu} \right] e^{-s(2-\tau)} + O(s^3 e^{-s(2+\tau)}), \end{aligned} \quad (44)$$

as $s \rightarrow \infty$. Therefore, the displacement transforms display regular behavior as $s \rightarrow 0$ as well as $s \rightarrow \infty$. Let us introduce the functions

$$\begin{aligned} c_2(s) &= C_2(s) + \frac{2\tau s}{3-4\nu} e^{-\tau s} + 2 \left[\frac{2(1-\tau)}{3-4\nu} s^2 + s\tau - 4 \frac{(1-\nu)(1-2\nu)}{3-4\nu} \right] e^{-s(2-\tau)}, \\ c_4(s) &= C_4(s) - \frac{2\tau s}{3-4\nu} e^{-\tau s} - 2 \left[\frac{2(1-\tau)}{3-4\nu} s^2 + s(2-\tau) + \frac{5-12\nu+8\nu^2}{3-4\nu} \right] e^{-s(2-\tau)}, \end{aligned} \quad (45)$$

which behave as $O(s^3 e^{-s(2+\tau)})$ as $s \rightarrow \infty$. Then, the Fourier transforms of the displacement field become

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{U}(s, \eta) &= (\eta - \tau) e^{-s|\tau-\eta|} + \left(\tau - \eta - \frac{2s\tau\eta}{3-4\nu} \right) e^{-s(\tau+\eta)} + \\ &\quad 8(1-\nu)(1-2\nu) \frac{\sinh \eta s}{s} e^{-s(2-\tau)} + [(3-4\nu)(\eta - \tau) - 2s(1-\eta)(1-\tau)] e^{-s(2-\tau-\eta)} \\ &\quad - \left[\frac{\eta}{3-4\nu} - (3-4\nu)\tau - 2s(1-\eta-\tau) + \frac{4\eta s^2}{3-4\nu} (1-\tau) \right] e^{-s(2-\tau+\eta)} + \bar{U}^*(s, \eta), \end{aligned} \quad (46)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{V}(s, \eta) &= \frac{3-4\nu}{s} \left[e^{-s|\tau-\eta|} - e^{-s(\tau+\eta)} \right] + |\eta - \tau| e^{-s|\tau-\eta|} - \left(\tau + \eta + \frac{2\tau s \eta}{3-4\nu} \right) e^{-s(\tau+\eta)} + \\ &\quad 2(5-12\nu+8\nu^2) \frac{\sinh \eta s}{s} e^{-s(2-\tau)} + [(3-4\nu)(2-\tau-\eta) + 2s(1-\eta)(1-\tau)] e^{-s(2-\tau-\eta)} \\ &\quad - \left[(3-4\nu)(2-\tau) + \frac{\eta}{3-4\nu} + 2s(1-\eta+\tau) + \frac{4\eta(1-\tau)}{3-4\nu} s^2 \right] e^{-s(2-\tau+\eta)} + \bar{V}^*(s, \eta), \end{aligned}$$

230 where the functions

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{U}^*(s, \eta) &= \frac{3-4\nu}{s} c_2(s) \sinh \eta s + \eta [c_2(s) \cosh \eta s + c_4(s) \sinh \eta s], \\ \bar{V}^*(s, \eta) &= \frac{3-4\nu}{s} c_4(s) \sinh \eta s - \eta [c_2(s) \sinh \eta s + c_4(s) \cosh \eta s], \end{aligned}$$

can be integrated numerically. Indeed, according to the asymptotic behavior of $c_2(s)$ and $c_4(s)$ as $s \rightarrow \infty$, it is easy to prove that functions $\bar{U}^*(s, \eta)$ and $\bar{V}^*(s, \eta)$ are finite as $s \rightarrow 0$ and behave as $O(s^3 e^{-s(1+\tau-\eta)})$ as $s \rightarrow \infty$.

Therefore, the displacement field follows from the inverse cosine and sine

235 Fourier transforms of (46) as

$$U(\xi, \eta) = \frac{4\tau\xi\eta(\eta-\tau)}{(\xi^2 + \eta^2 + \tau^2)^2 - 4\eta^2\tau^2} - \frac{4\tau\xi\eta(\tau+\eta)}{(3-4\nu)[\xi^2 + (\tau+\eta)^2]^2} + 4(1-2\nu)(1-\nu) \arctan \frac{2\eta\xi}{(2-\tau)^2 - \eta^2 + \xi^2} + U_R(\xi, \eta), \quad (47)$$

$$V(\xi, \eta) = -\frac{4\tau\eta\xi^2}{(\xi^2 + \eta^2 + \tau^2)^2 - 4\eta^2\tau^2} - \frac{2\tau\eta[(\tau+\eta)^2 - \xi^2]}{(3-4\nu)[\xi^2 + (\tau+\eta)^2]^2} + \frac{3-4\nu}{2} \ln \frac{\xi^2 + (\tau+\eta)^2}{\xi^2 + (\tau-\eta)^2} + \frac{5-12\nu+8\nu^2}{2} \ln \frac{\xi^2 + (2-\tau+\eta)^2}{\xi^2 + (2-\tau-\eta)^2} + V_R(\xi, \eta),$$

where

$$U_R(\xi, \eta) = \frac{(3-4\nu)(\eta-\tau)\xi}{(2-\eta-\tau)^2 + \xi^2} + \frac{[(3-4\nu)^2\tau - \eta]\xi}{(3-4\nu)[(2+\eta-\tau)^2 + \xi^2]} - \frac{4(1-\eta)(1-\tau)(2-\eta-\tau)\xi}{[(2-\eta-\tau)^2 + \xi^2]^2} + \frac{4\xi(1-\eta-\tau)(2+\eta-\tau)}{[(2+\eta-\tau)^2 + \xi^2]^2} - \frac{8\eta\xi(1-\tau)[3(2-\tau+\eta)^2 - \xi^2]}{(3-4\nu)[(2-\tau+\eta)^2 + \xi^2]^3} + \int_0^\infty \bar{U}^*(s, \eta) \sin s\xi ds, \quad (48)$$

$$V_R(\xi, \eta) = \frac{(3-4\nu)(2-\eta-\tau)^2}{\xi^2 + (2-\eta-\tau)^2} - \frac{(2+\eta-\tau)[(3-4\nu)^2(2-\tau) + \eta]}{(3-4\nu)[\xi^2 + (2+\eta-\tau)^2]} + 2(1-\eta)(1-\tau) \frac{(2-\eta-\tau)^2 - \xi^2}{[(2-\eta-\tau)^2 + \xi^2]^2} - 2(1+\eta-\tau) \frac{(2+\eta-\tau)^2 - \xi^2}{[(2+\eta-\tau)^2 + \xi^2]^2} - \frac{8\eta(1-\tau)(2-\tau+\eta)[(2-\tau+\eta)^2 - 3\xi^2]}{(3-4\nu)[(2-\tau+\eta)^2 + \xi^2]^3} + \int_0^\infty \bar{V}^*(s, \eta) \cos s\xi ds,$$

are regular functions of ξ, η and τ . In particular, the displacement along the y direction at $\xi = 0$ reads

$$V(0, \eta) = -\frac{2\tau\eta}{(3-4\nu)(\tau+\eta)^2} + (3-4\nu) \ln \frac{\tau+\eta}{\tau-\eta} + (5-12\nu+8\nu^2) \ln \frac{2-\tau+\eta}{2-\tau-\eta} + V_R(0, \eta), \quad (49)$$

where

$$V_R(0, \eta) = 3-4\nu - \frac{(3-4\nu)^2(2-\tau) + \eta}{(3-4\nu)(2+\eta-\tau)} + \frac{2(1-\eta)(1-\tau)}{(2-\eta-\tau)^2} - \frac{2(1+\eta-\tau)}{(2+\eta-\tau)^2} - \frac{8\eta(1-\tau)}{(3-4\nu)(2-\tau+\eta)^3} + \int_0^\infty \bar{V}^*(s, \eta) ds. \quad (50)$$

240 The 3D plots of functions $\bar{U}(s, \eta)$ and $\bar{V}(s, \eta)$ for $\tau = 0.6$ are provided in Appendix A for both the loading cases $F_x = 1$ and $F_y = 1$, see Figures A.12 and A.13 respectively. These results confirm the asymptotic behavior obtained in the present section.

3. An application: Laterally loaded pile embedded in an elastic layer

245 Let us consider now a vertical laterally loaded pile embedded in an elastic layer of height h on a rigid support, Figure 2. We assume that the pile is hinged

Figure 2: Sketch of a laterally loaded pile embedded in an elastic layer and hinged at the bottom.

at the bottom and loaded by a force F and couple C (per unit length) applied at the top of the pile. The pile is modelled as an Euler-Bernoulli elastic beam whose bending stiffness per unit length reads

$$B = \frac{E_0 b_0^3}{12(1 - \nu_0^2)}, \quad (51)$$

250 where b_0 is the thickness, E_0 and ν_0 are the Young modulus and Poisson's ratio of the pile. The pile is also subject to the unknown contact pressure $p(y)$ exchanged with the elastic layer along its height. The bending moment along the pile is then

$$M(y) = C - F(h - y) - \int_y^h (y - t) p(t) dt. \quad (52)$$

Since the boundary condition $M(0) = 0$ must hold true, it follows

$$\int_0^h p(t) t dt = F h - C. \quad (53)$$

255 Let $u(y)$ denote the transversal displacement of the pile, then the slope is given by

$$u'(y) = -\phi + \frac{1}{B} \int_y^h M(t) dt, \quad (54)$$

where ϕ is the rotation of the top cross section at $y = h$. By introducing eqn (52) in (54) one has

$$u'(y) = -\phi + \frac{1}{B} \left[C(h-y) - \frac{F}{2}(h-y)^2 + \frac{1}{2} \int_y^h (y-t)^2 p(t) dt \right]. \quad (55)$$

Integration of (55) by using the BC $u(0) = 0$ then gives

$$u(y) = -\phi y + \frac{1}{B} \left[C y \left(h - \frac{y}{2} \right) - \frac{F y}{2} \left(h^2 - h y + \frac{y^2}{3} \right) + \frac{1}{6} \int_0^h t^3 p(t) dt + \frac{1}{6} \int_y^h (y-t)^3 p(t) dt \right]. \quad (56)$$

260 Note that the kernel in eqn (56) is not singular and displays regular behavior as y tends to 0 or h . On the other side, the horizontal displacement of the elastic layer at $x = 0$ due to the contact pressure distribution $p(y)$ along the height of the layer can be calculated by using the Green's function (28) found in Section 2, namely

$$u(y) = \frac{1}{8\pi\mu(1-\nu)} \int_0^h \left[(3-4\nu) \ln \frac{c+y}{|c-y|} - \frac{2cy}{(3-4\nu)(c+y)^2} + (5-12\nu+8\nu^2) \ln \frac{2h-c+y}{2h-c-y} + U_R(0, \frac{y}{h}, \frac{c}{h}) \right] p(c) dc. \quad (57)$$

265 where $U_R(0, \eta, \tau)$ is defined in eqn (29) and its dependence on the point of load application c is made explicit. The kernel in eqn(57) is the sum of four terms. The first one is the Cauchy kernel, which has a logarithmic singularity for $y = c$, and thus it admits a square root singularity of the pressure $p(y)$ at $y = c$. Moreover, this term is not singular at $y = 0, h$ for $y \neq c$. The second term

270 is regular, whereas the third term displays a logarithmic singularity as both y and c tend to h . The last term is fully regular for $0 \leq y \leq h$, as discussed at the end of Sect. 2.1. Therefore, we can assume the contact pressure distribution in the form of a finite sum of Chebyshev functions displaying the classical square root singularity at $y = h$ only, namely

$$p(y) = \frac{B}{h^3} \sum_{n=0,1,2,\dots}^N p_n \frac{\mathcal{T}_n(y/h)}{\sqrt{1-(y/h)^2}}, \quad (58)$$

275 where \mathcal{T}_n is the Chebyshev polynomial of first kind of order n and p_n (for $n = 0, 1, 2, \dots, N$) are $N + 1$ unknown coefficients. By equating eqns (56) and (57), using (58) and the dimensionless variables introduced in (5), the following equation is obtained

$$\begin{aligned} \phi \eta - \chi \left(\eta - \frac{\eta^2}{2} \right) + \frac{\psi}{2} \left(\eta - \eta^2 + \frac{\eta^3}{3} \right) - \frac{\pi}{96} (3p_1 + p_3) + \\ \sum_{n=0}^N p_n \left[\beta D_n(\eta) - \frac{C_n(\eta)}{6} - \frac{\cos(n\pi/2)}{(n^2-1)(n^2-9)} \right] = 0, \end{aligned} \quad (59)$$

for $0 \leq \eta \leq 1$, where

$$\chi = \frac{Ch}{B}, \quad \psi = \frac{Fh^2}{B}, \quad \beta = \frac{B}{8\pi\mu(1-\nu)h^3},$$

280 are dimensionless quantities. The coefficient p_1 is given by condition (53) in terms of the even coefficients p_n for $n = 0, 2, \dots, N$, namely

$$p_1 = \frac{4}{\pi} \left[\psi - \chi + \sum_{n=0,2,\dots}^N p_n \frac{\cos(n\pi/2)}{n^2-1} \right]. \quad (60)$$

Moreover, $C_n(\eta)$ and $D_n(\eta)$ are defined by the following definite integrals

$$\begin{aligned} C_n(\eta) &= \int_{\eta}^1 (\eta - \tau)^3 \frac{\mathcal{T}_n(\tau)}{\sqrt{1-\tau^2}} d\tau, \\ D_n(\eta) &= \int_0^1 \left[(3-4\nu) \ln \frac{\tau + \eta}{|\tau - \eta|} - \frac{2\tau\eta}{(3-4\nu)(\tau + \eta)^2} + \right. \\ &\quad \left. (5-12\nu+8\nu^2) \ln \frac{2-\tau+\eta}{2-\tau-\eta} + U_R(0, \eta, \tau) \right] \frac{\mathcal{T}_n(\tau)}{\sqrt{1-\tau^2}} d\tau. \end{aligned} \quad (61)$$

The integral $C_n(\eta)$ can be expanded in the form

$$C_n(\eta) = \eta^3 C_n^{(0)}(\eta) - 3\eta^2 C_n^{(1)}(\eta) + 3\eta C_n^{(2)}(\eta) - C_n^{(3)}(\eta),$$

where

$$C_n^m(\eta) = \int_{\eta}^1 \frac{\mathcal{T}_n(\tau) \tau^m}{\sqrt{1-\tau^2}} d\tau. \quad (62)$$

285 Closed form expressions for the integrals $C_n^m(\eta)$, for $m = 0, 1, 2, 3$ and $0 \leq \eta \leq 1$, are calculated in Appendix B. Moreover, the term $D_n(\eta)$ in (61) can be split as

$$D_n(\eta) = (3 - 4\nu)L_n(\eta) - \frac{2\eta H_n(\eta)}{3 - 4\nu} + (5 - 12\nu + 8\nu^2)M_n(\eta) + G_n(\eta), \quad (63)$$

being

$$L_n(\eta) = \int_0^1 \ln \left| \frac{\eta + \tau}{\eta - \tau} \right| \frac{\mathcal{T}_n(\tau)}{\sqrt{1-\tau^2}} d\tau, \quad (64)$$

$$H_n(\eta) = \int_0^1 \frac{\tau}{(\eta + \tau)^2} \frac{\mathcal{T}_n(\tau)}{\sqrt{1-\tau^2}} d\tau, \quad (65)$$

$$M_n(\eta) = \int_0^1 \ln \frac{2 + \eta - \tau}{2 - \eta - \tau} \frac{\mathcal{T}_n(\tau)}{\sqrt{1-\tau^2}} d\tau, \quad (66)$$

$$G_n(\eta) = \int_0^1 g_n(\eta, \tau) \frac{\mathcal{T}_n(\tau)}{\sqrt{1-\tau^2}} d\tau, \quad (67)$$

$$g_n(\eta, \tau) = \int_0^{\infty} \bar{U}^*(s, \eta) ds,$$

for $0 \leq \eta \leq 1$. The definite integrals $L_n(\eta)$, $M_n(\eta)$, and $H_n(\eta)$ are calculated in
290 closed form in the Appendix B.

By using relation (60) for p_1 , then eqn (59) is solved for the $N + 1$ unknowns, ϕ and p_n with $n = 0, 2, 3, \dots, N$, by sampling eq(59) at the $N + 1$ Gauss-Chebyshev collocation points

$$\eta_j = \left[\cos \frac{(2j-1)\pi}{4(N+1)} \right]^2, \quad (j = 1, 2, \dots, N+1). \quad (68)$$

Therefore, the collocation method leads to the following compatibility condition
295 at the interface between the layer and the pile

$$\begin{aligned} \phi \eta_j - \chi \left(\eta_j - \frac{\eta_j^2}{2} \right) + \frac{\psi}{2} \left(\eta_j - \eta_j^2 + \frac{\eta_j^3}{3} \right) - \frac{\pi}{96} (3p_1 + p_3) + \\ \sum_{n=0}^N p_n \left[\beta D_n(\eta_j) - \frac{C_n(\eta_j)}{6} - \frac{\cos(n\pi/2)}{(n^2-1)(n^2-9)} \right] = 0, \end{aligned} \quad (69)$$

for $j = 1, 2, \dots, N + 1$, being

$$D_n(\eta_j) = (3 - 4\nu) L_n(\eta_j) - \frac{2\eta_j H_n(\eta_j)}{3 - 4\nu} + \sum_{k=1}^{N+1} \frac{\pi g_n(\eta_j, \eta_k) \mathcal{T}_n(\eta_k)}{N + 1} \sqrt{\frac{\eta_k}{1 + \eta_k}}, \quad (70)$$

where the Gauss-Chebyshev quadrature are used to compute the integral $G_n(\eta_j)$ defined in (67). Moreover, the terms $g_n(\eta_j, \eta_k)$, for $j, k = 1, 2, \dots, N + 1$, in (70) can be evaluated numerically by using the Gauss-Laguerre quadrature for M integration points, namely

$$g_n(\eta_j, \eta_k) = \sum_{i=1}^M \frac{\bar{U}^*(s_i, \eta_j, \eta_k) e^{s_i} s_i}{(M + 1)^2 \mathcal{L}_{M+1}^2(s_i)}, \quad (71)$$

where s_i , for $i = 1, 2, \dots, M$, are the M roots of the Laguerre polynomial $\mathcal{L}_M(s)$ of order M . In the following, it has been assumed $M = 2N$. Alternatively, $g_n(\eta_j, \eta_k)$ can be calculated numerically by transforming the integral over an infinite region (67) into an integral over the finite interval $[0, 1]$ by using the transformation rule $s = \tanh^{-1} z$, namely

$$g_n(\eta_j, \eta_k) = \int_0^1 \frac{\bar{U}^*(\operatorname{arctanh} z, \eta_j, \eta_k)}{1 - z^2} dz. \quad (72)$$

4. Results and discussion

4.1. Layer subjected to an internal point load

The main results in terms of displacement and stress fields occurring in the layer subjected to a horizontal point load F_x are discussed first by assuming, for sake of definiteness, $c = h/3$ (i.e. $\tau = 1/3$) and $\nu = 0.15$. The analytic results are compared with the numerical solution provided by the FEM code COMSOL Multiphysics v.5.6 ©.

The analytic results on the displacement and stress fields are obtained by assuming $N = 38$. On the other side, the FEM model simulates a finite layer of height h and finite length of $20h$. Although the FEM model accounts for the shear stress component at the interface between the elastic layer and the pile, this effect will be shown to be negligible in the cases investigated here (slender pile).

The dimensionless distributions of the horizontal displacement $U(0, \eta)$ and shear stress $\Sigma_{xy}(0, \eta)$ along the height of the layer are shown in Figure 3(a). From now on, solid continuous line are used for the analytic model whilst dashed

(a) At $\xi = 0$. (b) At $\eta = 1$ (free-surface).

Figure 3: Comparison between analytical and FEM results in terms of dimensionless displacement and stress fields for the loading case $F_x = 1$ acting at $\tau = 1/3$ for $\nu = 0.15$.

lines denote FEM solution. As expected for skew-symmetric loading conditions, one has $V(0, \eta) = \Sigma_{xx}(0, \eta) = \Sigma_{yy}(0, \eta) = 0$. Excellent agreement between analytical and FEM results are found, except in the neighbourhood of the load application point $\eta = \tau$, where numerical results are affected by noise owing to the singular behavior of the stress field. As predicted by the Kelvin solution, both the displacement and stress fields exhibit an exponential decay (11). This fact is confirmed by Figure 3(b), where the dimensionless displacements at the free surface of the layer, $U(\xi, 1)$ and $V(\xi, 1)$, and the dimensionless stress $\Sigma_{xx}(\xi, 1)$ are plotted. Also in this case, a very good agreement is observed between the analytical and FEM predictions. For $\xi > 4$ slight oscillations affect the trend of the stress component Σ_{xx} due to the finite number of terms considered in the series representation.

Similarly to Figure 3, Figure 4 displays the dimensionless displacement and stress fields in the layer due to a vertical point load F_y acting at $\tau = 1/3$. In particular, the displacement and stress fields along the height of the layer at

$\xi = 0$ are shown in Figure 4(a). Differently from the case $F_x = 1$, now the

Figure 4: Comparison between analytical and FEM results in terms of dimensionless displacement and stress fields for the loading case $F_y = 1$ acting at $\tau = 1/3$ for $\nu = 0.15$.

displacement component $U(0, \eta)$ and the shear stress $\Sigma_{xy}(0, \eta)$ vanishes due to symmetry. Figure 4(b) shows that, similarly to the previous horizontal loading
340 condition, all the fields exhibit a non-monotonic behavior at the free surface (i.e. at $\eta = 1$). Here, the stress component $\Sigma_{xx}(\xi, 1)$ displays a local minimum at $\xi \approx 0.7$, whereas the horizontal displacement $U(\xi, 1)$ displays a maximum at $\xi \approx 0.45$.

The contour plot of the displacement components of the layer, for $\xi \in [0, 2]$
345 and $\eta \in [0, 1]$, are reported in Figure 5 and 6 for the loading conditions $F_x = 1$ and $F_y = 1$, respectively, and for $\tau = 1/3$. In the same way, the contour plot of the dimensionless stress components $\Sigma_{xx}(\xi, \eta)$, $\Sigma_{yy}(\xi, \eta)$ and $\Sigma_{xy}(\xi, \eta)$ are given in Figure 7 and 8. The iso-line shown in Figures (5-8) highlight the displacements and stress concentrations in the neighbourhood of the application
350 point of the load. As expected from the BCs (2), the displacement field vanishes at the rigid base ($\eta = 0$) for both the loading conditions, and the same holds for stress components $\Sigma_{yy}(\xi, \eta)$ and $\Sigma_{xy}(\xi, \eta)$ at the free surface ($\eta = 1$) consistently with BCs (3). In the neighbourhood of the load application point $(0, 1/3)$ the obtained results reproduce the Kelvin solution.

Figure 5: Contour plots of the dimensionless displacements $U(\xi, \eta)$ and $V(\xi, \eta)$ for the loading case $F_x = 1$ acting at $\tau = 1/3$ for $\nu = 0.15$.

Figure 6: Contour plot of the dimensionless displacements $U(\xi, \eta)$ and $V(\xi, \eta)$ for the loading case $F_y = 1$ acting at $\tau = 1/3$ for $\nu = 0.15$.

355 The influence of the load application point on the displacement field at the
point $(0, 1)$ at the top of the layer is investigated in the following. In particular,
the variations of the displacement components at the top of the layer $U(0, 1)$
and $V(0, 1)$ induced by a horizontal point force F_x and by a vertical point force
 F_y , respectively, are displayed in Figure 9 for the two extremal values of the
360 Poisson's ratio of the elastic layer, namely for $\nu = 0$ and $\nu = 0.5$. It can be ob-
served that the Poisson's ratio significantly affects the solution, and for a nearly
incompressible layer ($\nu \rightarrow 0.5$), these two displacement components are almost
coincident. Moreover, as ν decreases starting from $\nu = 0.5$, both components of
the displacement fields at the free surface increase, specially the vertical com-

Figure 7: Contour plots of the dimensionless stresses $\Sigma_{xx}(\xi, \eta)$, $\Sigma_{yy}(\xi, \eta)$ and $\Sigma_{xy}(\xi, \eta)$ for the loading case $F_x = 1$ acting at $\tau = 1/3$.

365 ponents $V(0, 1)$. Note also that, for $\tau \rightarrow 1$, both surface displacements diverge. Indeed, in such a situation the obtained results recover the Cerruti and Flamant solutions for a half plane loaded at its surface by horizontal and normal point forces [?], respectively. Moreover, as expected, $U(0, 1) = V(0, 1) = 0$ as $\tau \rightarrow 0$ because, in such a case, the applied load acts on the rigid support.

370 *4.2. Sheet pile embedded in a soil layer*

In the present Section the problem of a laterally loaded pile embedded in an elastic soil layer is studied as a relevant application, on the basis of the Green's function for the horizontal displacement found in Section 3. A horizontal force F and a couple C (both per unit length) act at the top of the pile (see Figure 2),
 375 which is assumed to be hinged at the bottom due to the presence of the rigid base (bedrock). The data assumed for the soil-pile system are listed in Table 1

Figure 8: Contour plots of the dimensionless stresses $\Sigma_{xx}(\xi, \eta)$, $\Sigma_{yy}(\xi, \eta)$ and $\Sigma_{xy}(\xi, \eta)$ for the loading case $F_y = 1$ acting at $\tau = 1/3$.

(symbols abide those used in Section 3). In particular, the elastic constants

Element	Amount	Values	Unit
Layer	μ	50	MPa
	ν	0.15	/
	h	20	m
Sheet Pile	E_0	30	GPa
	ν_0	0.2	/
	b_0	1.0	m

Table 1: Parameters of the soil-pile system

of the layer comply with those of a sandy soil actually investigated in [?]. Accordingly to the adopted parameters, it follows that $\beta \approx 30.475 \cdot 10^{-3}$, which

Figure 9: Dimensionless displacements $U(0, 1)$ (black lines) and $V(0, 1)$ (grey lines) induced respectively by $F_x = 1$ and $F_y = 1$, varying the dimensionless coordinates of the application point of the load (τ): case with $\nu = 0$ (dashed lines) and case with $\nu = 0.5$ (dotted lines).

380 denotes a slender pile embedded in a stiff soil layer.

The main results in terms of dimensionless filed, contact pressure at the pile-soil interface, horizontal displacement, shearing force and bending moment arising in the pile are shown in Figure 10 by assuming $F = 1N$ and $C = Fh/20$. As for the previous Section, the numerical simulations of the pile-soil system
 385 are modelled by using COMSOL Multiphysics[®].

As shown in Figure 10, the analytical predictions are almost coincident with the FEM results. A slight gap between the analytical and FEM predictions occurs in the bending moment in the range $0.85 \leq \eta \leq 0.95$, as shown in Figure 10(d). This difference may be due to numerical approximations related
 390 to the series expansions. As expected, both the shearing force and the bending moment decay rapidly far from the loaded top of the pile. Such trend is more pronounced for the shearing force, which practically vanishes for $\eta < 0.3$. Except for the horizontal displacement, all quantities display non-monotonic trends with η . In particular, the peak of the bending moment occurs at $\eta \approx 0.9$ where
 395 the shearing force is null. The shearing force exhibits a relative maximum at $\eta \approx 0.8$, where the contact pressure is vanishing, in agreement with the

Figure 10: Dimensionless variations of contact pressure, displacement and internal forces along the pile loaded by a horizontal force $F = 1N$ and a couple $C = Fh/20$ at its top: analytical predictions (solid lines) and FEM results (dashed lines). Reference is made to the parameters listed in Table 1.

equilibrium equations of the EB beam theory.

For a pile loaded by an external transversal force F only (couple C is zero), Figure 11 shows the effect of the relative stiffness of the pile with respect to the elastic layer according to the selected values of the parameter β .

In particular, for low values of β (i.e. compliant pile embedded in a stiff soil), the contact pressure and, in turn, the shearing force and the bending moment concentrate at the top of the pile, near the application point of the load F . On the other hand, as β increases, the contact pressure and the internal forces extend towards the inner part of the pile. The same holds true also for the horizontal displacement, which displays a monotonic trend along the height of the pile, see Figure 11(b). Note also that, for very stiff piles (i.e. $\beta > 10^{-3}$),

Figure 11: Dimensionless variations of the contact pressure, displacement and internal forces along the pile loaded by a horizontal force F for different values of the relative stiffness parameter β .

also the contact pressure exhibits a monotonic trend and it maintains the same sign along the height of the layer, as shown in Figure 11(a). In such a situation,
 410 it is worth noticing that the shearing force at the bottom of the pile is of the same order of magnitude (about one half) of that achieved at the top, which is equal to the applied external force, see Figure 11(c).

More general loading and constraint conditions for the pile could be easily accounted for. In particular, a pile embedded in the soil layer, not constrained at
 415 its bottom, could be studied by assuming again expression (58) for the contact pressure, but introducing a scaling of the y coordinate in order to have a square root singularity of the contact pressure also at the bottom end of the pile. In this case, a further balance condition on the horizontal forces acting on the pile must be imposed.

420 **5. Concluding remarks**

The 2D problem of a homogeneous elastic layer of finite height, infinitely extended and subjected to an internal point force under plane strain conditions is investigated analytically. The solution of the 2D Kelvin problem is used as a particular solution, which reproduces the singular behavior in the neighbouring
425 of the load application point. Then, an homogeneous solution is superposed to the previous one in order to fulfil the BCs at the top and at the bottom of the layer. The representation of the unknown displacement field through Fourier transforms allows obtaining a system of 2 ODEs, which is solved in closed form. The inverse Fourier transforms of the most singular terms is handled
430 analytically, whereas the regular terms is calculated through the Gauss-Laguerre quadrature. The main results in terms of displacements and stresses in the layer are provided, finding excellent agreement with respect to the FEM predictions. In particular, the obtained analytical results confirm that both displacements and stresses are singular at the load application point. For a layer subjected
435 to an internal point force, stresses and displacements at the free surface exhibit non-monotonic behavior. Moreover, it is shown that Poisson's ratio can affect significantly the behavior of the layer. In particular, as ν decreases starting from $\nu = 0.5$, both the horizontal and vertical components of the surface displacement increase, whereas for an almost incompressible layer, such components coincide.
440 As expected, as the load application point approaches the layer surface, therein the surface displacements tend to diverge according to the Cerruti and Flamant solutions for an elastic half plane.

The interaction of a pile embedded in an elastic layer and laterally loaded at its top is addressed as a relevant application of the obtained Green's function.
445 We found that varying the relative stiffness parameter of the pile-soil system, the distribution of the internal forces in the pile changes significantly. In particular, for piles compliant with respect the hosting layer, the bending moment and shearing force tend to concentrate at the top of the pile. The same holds true for the contact pressure, which rapidly increases at the surface of the layer.

450 The Green's functions derived here can be efficiently used for calculating the
 2D mechanical interaction between an elastic layer and a pile embedded in it,
 under various boundary conditions and also taking into account for frictional
 contact behavior. In particular, the influence of friction on the buckling load of
 piles embedded in an elastic layer will be investigated in a forthcoming works.

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Appendices

**Appendix A. Graphical representations of the Fourier transforms of
 the displacement field**

Figure A.12 and A.13 show the behavior of the normalised Fourier trans-

Figure A.12: Dimensionless Green Functions for the loading case $F_x = 1$ acting at $\tau = 0.6$.

465 forms $\bar{U}(s,\eta)$ and $\bar{V}(s,\eta)$ of the displacement fields for $F_x = 1$ and $F_y = 1$,
 respectively, acting at $\tau = c/h = 0.6$. As shown, the plots confirm the asymp-
 totic behavior of the amplitudes of the displacements transforms for $s \rightarrow 0$ as

Figure A.13: Dimensionless Green Functions for the loading case $F_y = 1$ acting at $\tau = 0.6$.

well as for $s \rightarrow +\infty$. In particular, it is easy to show that for the loading case $F_x = 1$ one has

$$\lim_{s \rightarrow 0} \bar{U}(s, \eta) = 4(1 - \nu)(\eta + \tau - |\eta - \tau|), \quad \lim_{s \rightarrow 0} \bar{V}(s, \eta) = 0,$$

470 whereas for the loading case $F_y = 1$ it is

$$\lim_{s \rightarrow 0} \bar{U}(s, \eta) = 0, \quad \lim_{s \rightarrow 0} \bar{V}(s, \eta) = 2(1 - 2\nu)(\eta + \tau - |\eta - \tau|).$$

Appendix B. Calculation of definite integrals involving Chebyshev polynomials

The Chebyshev polynomials of the first kind, \mathcal{T}_n may be defined through the identity:

$$\mathcal{T}_n(\tau) = \cos(n \arccos \tau), \quad (\text{B.1})$$

475 where $0 \leq \cos^{-1} \tau \leq \pi$ and $n \in \mathbb{N}_0$ represents the order of the polynomial. They form a complete orthogonal set in the interval $[-1, 1]$ with respect to the weight function $(1 - \tau^2)^{-1/2}$, namely:

$$\int_{-1}^1 \frac{\mathcal{T}_n(\tau) \mathcal{T}_m(\tau)}{\sqrt{1 - \tau^2}} d\tau = \begin{cases} \pi/2 & \text{if } n = m \neq 0, \\ \pi & \text{if } n = m = 0, \\ 0 & \text{if } n \neq m. \end{cases} \quad (\text{B.2})$$

The Chebyshev polynomials of the second kind \mathcal{U}_n are defined by:

$$\mathcal{U}_n(\tau) = \frac{\sin[(n+1)\cos^{-1}\tau]}{\sin(\cos^{-1}\tau)}. \quad (\text{B.3})$$

They are orthogonal with respect the weight $(1-t)^{1/2}$, namely:

$$\int_{-1}^1 \mathcal{U}_n(\tau)\mathcal{U}_m(\tau)\sqrt{1-\tau^2}d\tau = \frac{\pi}{2}\delta_{nm} \quad (\text{B.4})$$

480 where δ_{nm} is the Kronecker delta.

Appendix B.1. Calculation of $C_n^m(\eta)$ in (B.8-B.11)

In order to obtain the results (B.8)-(B.11), let us define

making the substitution $\tau = \cos\theta$, the definite integrals (62) can be transformed in the form:

$$C_n^m(\eta) = \int_0^{\arccos\eta} \cos(n\theta)(\cos\theta)^m d\theta. \quad (\text{B.5})$$

485 By using the recursive (2.538.1) provided in [?], namely

$$\int \cos n\theta (\cos\theta)^m d\theta = \frac{1}{n+m} \left[(\cos\theta)^m \cos(n\theta) + m \int \cos(n-1)\theta (\cos\theta)^{m-1} d\theta \right] \quad (\text{B.6})$$

which holds for $n+m \neq 0$, one has

$$C_n^m(\eta) = \frac{1}{n+m} \left[\eta^m \mathcal{U}_{n-1}(\eta)\sqrt{1-\eta^2} + m C_{n-1}^{m-1}(\eta) \right], \quad (\text{B.7})$$

and thus

$$C_n^{(0)}(\eta) = \begin{cases} \cos^{-1}\eta, & \text{if } n=0 \\ \frac{\mathcal{U}_{n-1}(\eta)}{n} \sqrt{1-\eta^2}, & \text{if } n \neq 0 \end{cases}, \quad (\text{B.8})$$

$$C_n^{(1)}(\eta) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{2} (\eta \sqrt{1-\eta^2} + \cos^{-1}\eta), & \text{if } n=1 \\ \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{\mathcal{U}_{n-2}(\eta)}{n-1} + \frac{\mathcal{U}_n(\eta)}{n+1} \right] \sqrt{1-\eta^2}, & \text{if } n \neq 1 \end{cases}, \quad (\text{B.9})$$

$$C_n^{(2)}(\eta) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{4} [\eta(2\eta^2+1)\sqrt{1-\eta^2} + \cos^{-1}\eta], & \text{if } n=2 \\ \frac{1}{4} \left[\frac{\mathcal{U}_{n-3}(\eta)}{n-2} + \frac{\mathcal{U}_{n+1}(\eta)}{n+2} \right] \sqrt{1-\eta^2} + \frac{C_n^{(0)}(\eta)}{2}, & \text{if } n \neq 2 \end{cases} \quad (\text{B.10})$$

$$C_n^{(3)}(\eta) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{8} \left[\frac{\eta}{3} (16\eta^4 + 2\eta^2 + 3)\sqrt{1-\eta^2} + \cos^{-1}\eta \right], & \text{if } n=3 \\ \frac{1}{8} \left[\frac{\mathcal{U}_{n-4}(\eta)}{n-3} + \frac{\mathcal{U}_{n+2}(\eta)}{n+3} \right] \sqrt{1-\eta^2} + \frac{3}{4} C_n^{(1)}(\eta), & \text{if } n \neq 3 \end{cases} \quad (\text{B.11})$$

where \mathcal{U}_n is the Chebyshev polynomial of second kind of order n .

Appendix B.2. Calculation of $L_n(\eta)$ in (B.23)

490 Introducing the substitutions $\tau = \cos \theta$ and then integrating by parts, the integral $L_0(\eta)$ defined in (64) becomes

$$L_0(\eta) = 2\eta \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{2}} \frac{\theta \sin \theta}{\eta^2 - \cos^2 \theta} d\theta. \quad (\text{B.12})$$

Then, by using the result (3.812.7) in [?], namely

$$\int_0^{\frac{\pi}{2}} \frac{\theta \sin \theta}{\sin^2 t - \cos^2 \theta} d\theta = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{\sin(2k+1)t}{(2k+1)^2}, \quad (\text{B.13})$$

and the definition (B.3) of the Chebyshev polynomials of the second kind, the result provided in eqn (B.23) for $n = 0$ is obtained.

495 For $n \neq 0$, making the substitutions $\tau = \cos(t/2)$ and $\eta = \cos(\alpha/2)$ and then integrating by parts, the integral $L_n(\eta)$ introduced in (64) becomes

$$L_n(\eta) = -\frac{2\eta}{n} \int_0^{\pi} \frac{\sin(t/2) \sin(nt/2)}{\cos t - \cos \alpha} dt, \quad (\text{B.14})$$

Now, by using the trigonometric identity

$$2 \sin \frac{t}{2} \sin \frac{nt}{2} = \cos \frac{n-1}{2}t - \cos \frac{n+1}{2}t, \quad (\text{B.15})$$

and the result [?]

$$\int_0^{\pi} \frac{\cos mt}{\cos t - \cos \alpha} dt = \pi \frac{\sin m \alpha}{\sin \alpha}, \quad (\text{B.16})$$

which holds for m integer, from (B.14) it follows that

$$L_n(\eta) = \frac{\pi}{n} \cos \frac{n\alpha}{2} = \frac{\pi}{n} \mathcal{T}_n(\eta) \quad \text{for } n \text{ odd}, \quad (\text{B.17})$$

500 as reported in (B.23).

For n even, let us denote with $S_{n/2}(\alpha)$ the integral in (B.14). Then, by using the following trigonometric identity

$$\sin(m+1)t - 2a \sin mt + \sin(m-1)t = 2(\cos t - a) \sin mt, \quad (\text{B.18})$$

which holds for every integer m and real a , it can be proved that for $a = \cos \alpha$ then $S_m(\alpha)$ satisfies the following recurrence equation

$$S_{m+1}(\alpha) - 2 \cos \alpha S_m(\alpha) + S_{m-1}(\alpha) = 2 \int_0^{\pi} \sin \frac{t}{2} \sin mt dt = -\frac{8m \cos m \pi}{4m^2 - 1} \quad (\text{B.19})$$

505 with the initial conditions

$$\begin{aligned} S_0(\alpha) &= 0, \\ S_1(\alpha) &= \int_0^\pi \frac{\sin(t/2) \sin t}{\cos t - \cos \alpha} dt = \sin \frac{\alpha}{2} \ln \frac{1 + \sin(\alpha/2)}{1 - \sin(\alpha/2)} - 2. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B.20})$$

Eqn (B.19) is a linear and inhomogeneous recurrence equation with constant coefficients, satisfying the initial conditions (B.20), which can be solved by the method of undetermined coefficients as the sum of a particular solution and the fundamental set of solutions of the homogeneous equation, as illustrated in Sect. 510 2.4 of [?], namely

$$S_m(\alpha) = \frac{1}{\sin \alpha} \left[S_1(\alpha) \sin m\alpha - 8 \sum_{k=1}^{m-1} \frac{k \cos k\pi}{4k^2 - 1} \sin(m-k)\alpha \right], \quad (\text{B.21})$$

and thus

$$L_n(\eta) = -\frac{2\eta}{n} S_{n/2}(2 \arccos \eta), \quad \text{for } n \text{ even}, \quad (\text{B.22})$$

as reported in (B.23) after the introduction of the Chebyshev polynomials of the second kind (B.3) instead of the trigonometric functions of multiples of the angle $\alpha = 2 \arccos \eta$.

$$L_n(\eta) = \begin{cases} \frac{\pi}{n} \mathcal{T}_n(\eta), & \text{for } n \text{ odd}, \\ 4\eta \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{\mathcal{U}_{2k}(\sqrt{1-\eta^2})}{(2k+1)^2}, & \text{for } n = 0, \\ \frac{2}{n} \left[\left(1 - \sqrt{1-\eta^2} \operatorname{arctanh} \sqrt{1-\eta^2} \right) \mathcal{U}_{n-1}(\eta) \right. \\ \quad \left. + \sum_{k=1}^{n/2-1} \frac{4k \cos k\pi}{4k^2 - 1} \mathcal{U}_{n-2k-1}(\eta) \right], & \text{for } n \text{ even } (n \neq 0). \end{cases} \quad (\text{B.23})$$

$$(\text{B.24})$$

515 *Appendix B.3. Calculation of $M_n(\eta)$ in (66)*

Using the properties of the logarithmic function, the integral $M_n(\eta)$ defined in (66) with $\eta \geq 1$ can be split as

$$M_n(\eta) = N_n(2 + \eta) - N_n(2 - \eta), \quad (\text{B.25})$$

where

$$N_n(\eta) = \int_0^1 \ln(\eta - \tau) \frac{\mathcal{T}_n(\tau)}{\sqrt{1 - \tau^2}} d\tau. \quad (\text{B.26})$$

Introducing the substitutions $\tau = \cos \theta$ and then integrating by parts, the integral $N_n(\eta)$ becomes

$$N_n(\eta) = \frac{1}{n} \left(\ln \eta \sin \frac{n\pi}{2} - \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{2}} \frac{\sin \theta \sin n\theta}{\eta - \cos \theta} d\theta \right). \quad (\text{B.27})$$

Let us denote with $Z_n(\eta)$ the integral in (B.27), namely

$$Z_n(\eta) = \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{2}} \frac{\sin \theta \sin n\theta}{\eta - \cos \theta} d\theta. \quad (\text{B.28})$$

Then, by using the trigonometric identity (B.18) for $a = \eta$, it follows that $Z_n(\eta)$ satisfies the following recurrence equation

$$Z_{n+1}(\eta) - 2\eta Z_n(\eta) + Z_{n-1}(\eta) = \omega_n, \quad (\text{B.29})$$

where

$$\omega_n = -2 \int_0^\pi \sin \theta \sin n\theta d\theta = \begin{cases} -\frac{\pi}{2} & \text{for } n = 1, \\ \frac{2n}{n^2 - 1} \cos \frac{n\pi}{2}, & \text{for } n \neq 1. \end{cases} \quad (\text{B.30})$$

with the initial conditions

$$\begin{aligned} Z_0(\eta) &= 0, \\ Z_1(\eta) &= \int_0^\pi \frac{\sin^2 \theta}{\eta - \cos \theta} d\theta \\ &= 1 + \frac{\pi}{2}(\eta - \sqrt{\eta^2 - 1}) + [2 \arctan(\eta + \sqrt{\eta^2 - 1}) - \pi] \sqrt{\eta^2 - 1}. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B.31})$$

Eqn (B.29) is a linear and inhomogeneous recurrence equation with constant coefficients, satisfying the initial conditions (B.31), which can be solved by the method of undetermined coefficients as the sum of a particular solution and the fundamental set of solutions of the homogeneous equation, as illustrated in Sect.

2.4 of [?], namely

$$\begin{aligned} Z_n(\eta) &= \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{2 + \pi \eta}{\sqrt{\eta^2 - 1}} + 4 \arctan(\eta + \sqrt{\eta^2 - 1}) - 3\pi \right] \sinh(n \operatorname{arccosh} \eta) + \\ &\quad \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} \omega_k \frac{\sinh[(n - k) \operatorname{arccosh} \eta]}{\sqrt{\eta^2 - 1}}, \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B.32})$$

and thus

$$M_n(\eta) = \frac{1}{n} \left[\ln \frac{2+\eta}{2-\eta} \sin \frac{n\pi}{2} - Z_n(2+\eta) + Z_n(2-\eta) \right], \quad (\text{B.33})$$

for $n \neq 0$. Moreover, as $n \rightarrow 0$ from eqn (B.27) it follows

$$N_0(\eta) = \frac{\pi}{2} \ln \eta - \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{2}} \frac{\theta \sin \theta}{\eta - \cos \theta} d\theta. \quad (\text{B.34})$$

Then, by using the following Fourier series expansion

$$\frac{\sin \theta}{\eta - \cos \theta} = 2 \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} e^{-k \operatorname{arccosh} \eta} \sin k\theta, \quad (\text{B.35})$$

one has

$$\int_0^{\frac{\pi}{2}} \frac{\theta \sin \theta}{\eta - \cos \theta} d\theta = 2 \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{e^{-k \operatorname{arccosh} \eta}}{k^2} \left(2 \sin \frac{k\pi}{2} - k\pi \cos \frac{k\pi}{2} \right). \quad (\text{B.36})$$

535 Therefore

$$N_0(\eta) = \frac{\pi}{2} (\operatorname{arccosh} \eta - \ln 2) - \frac{1}{2} e^{-\operatorname{arccosh} \eta} \Phi \left(-e^{-2 \operatorname{arccosh} \eta}, 2, \frac{1}{2} \right), \quad (\text{B.37})$$

where

$$\Phi(z, s, a) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{z^k}{(k+a)^s}, \quad (|z| < 1, a > 0) \quad (\text{B.38})$$

is the Lerch transcendent function [?]. Finally

$$M_0(\eta) = N_0(2+\eta) - N_0(2-\eta). \quad (\text{B.39})$$

Appendix B.4. Calculation of $H_n(\eta)$ in (65)

Let us define with

$$J_n(\eta) = \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{2}} \frac{\cos \theta \cos n\theta}{\eta + \cos \theta} d\theta. \quad (\text{B.40})$$

540 Then, by using the following trigonometric identity

$$\cos n\theta + 2\eta \cos(n-1)\theta + \cos(n-2)\theta = 2(\eta + \cos \theta) \cos(n-1)\theta, \quad (\text{B.41})$$

which holds for every n integer, it follows that $J_n(\eta)$ satisfies the following recurrence equation

$$\begin{aligned} J_n(\eta) + 2\eta J_{n-1}(\eta) + J_{n-2}(\eta) &= 2 \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{2}} \cos(n-1)\theta \cos\theta d\theta \\ &= \begin{cases} \frac{\pi}{2} & \text{for } n = 2, \\ \frac{-2 \sin(n\pi/2)}{n(n-2)} & \text{for } n \neq 2, \end{cases} \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B.42})$$

which holds for $n \geq 2$, with the initial conditions

$$J_0(\eta) = \frac{\pi}{2} - \frac{\eta \tanh \sqrt{1-\eta^2}}{\sqrt{1-\eta^2}}, \quad J_1(\eta) = 1 - \eta J_0(\eta), \quad (\text{B.43})$$

which can be calculated by substituting $t = \tan(\theta/2)$ in (B.40) for $n = 0, 1$.

545 Again, eqn (B.42) is a linear and inhomogeneous recurrence equation with constant coefficients, satisfying the initial conditions (B.43), which admits the solution [?]

$$J_n(\eta) = \cos n\pi \left[J_0(\eta) \mathcal{T}_n(\eta) - \mathcal{U}_{n-1}(\eta) + \sum_{k=2}^n \psi_k \mathcal{U}_{n-k}(\eta) \right], \quad (\text{B.44})$$

where

$$\psi_k = \begin{cases} \frac{\pi}{2} & \text{for } k = 2, \\ \frac{2 \sin(k\pi/2)}{k(k-2)} & \text{for } k \neq 2. \end{cases} \quad (\text{B.45})$$

Then, from (65) and (B.40) one has

$$H_n(\eta) = -\frac{dJ_n(\eta)}{d\eta}, \quad (\text{B.46})$$

550 and thus, by taking the derivative of (B.44) with respect to η , from (B.46) it follows

$$\begin{aligned} H_n(\eta) &= \frac{(-1)^{n+1}}{1-\eta^2} \left\{ \left(n+1 - \frac{\operatorname{arctanh} \sqrt{1-\eta^2}}{\sqrt{1-\eta^2}} \right) \mathcal{T}_n(\eta) - \eta \mathcal{U}_{n-1}(\eta) + \right. \\ &\quad \left. \sum_{k=2}^n \psi_k \left[(n-k+2) \eta \mathcal{U}_{n-k}(\eta) - (n-k+1) \mathcal{U}_{n-k+1}(\eta) \right] \right\} + \\ &\quad n(-1)^{n+1} \left(\frac{\pi}{2} - \eta \frac{\operatorname{arctanh} \sqrt{1-\eta^2}}{\sqrt{1-\eta^2}} \right) \mathcal{U}_{n-1}(\eta). \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B.47})$$

References